

as under :

From the above reaction it can be inferred that a large excess of the less basic aromatic diamine can replace more basic ammonia, but the rate of reaction is very slow with aromatic diamines as an incoming amine.

The amine exchange reaction can occur with good yield when the reacting amine is more basic than the amine initially used to form the imine complex^{8,9}. Thus, ethylene diamine is replaced by 1,2-diamino propane as reported earlier⁴. In addition, such reactions appear to be favoured by the presence of a large excess of exchanging amine.

It has also been observed that the amine exchange reaction between N,N'-o-phenylene[salicylideneaminato, 1-(2-hydroxy-phenyl) ethylideneaminato]Ni(II) and ethylene diamine did not take place, even though the aliphatic diamine is more basic than the aromatic diamine.

It may be suggested that the coordinated aromatic diamines may to some extent involve back donation from the metal resulting in some double bond character to metal-nitrogen bond and lowering the effective positive charge on the azomethine carbon. Therefore, carbon of azomethine group would not encourage nucleophilic attack. This indicates the higher stability of aromatic diamine Schiff base complexes than that of aliphatic diamine.

The visible absorption spectra of the complexes obtained from both the methods show shoulder between 560 to 575 nm. This shows that the compounds are square planar in structure. Such structure is also supported by diamagnetic nature of all the complexes.

The ir spectra of the 1:1:1 nickel(II) compounds do not exhibit the band in the 3400 cm⁻¹ range indicating that -OH hydrogens of aldehyde or ketone get dissociated after complexation. The band at 1625 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the aldehydic and ketonic C=O. The shift in value is due to the coordination. This band, however, disappears and a new band at 1600 cm⁻¹ appears in the imine Schiff base complexes. This corresponds to C=N stretch and indicates the formation of Schiff base. In the mixed imine nickel(II) Schiff base complexes the band at 3300 cm⁻¹ corresponds to -N-H stretching frequency. The disappearance of the 3300 cm⁻¹ band after amine exchange reaction can be attributed to the replacement of the N-H hydrogen by an aromatic diamine. The two weak bands observed at 2920 and 2860 cm⁻¹ correspond to C-H stretching frequency due to -CH₃ group and aldehydic C-H, respectively.

The percentage loss in weights on heating, at various temperatures indicate the gradual decomposition of the complexes. The abrupt change in weight shows the decomposition of the ligand. The order of thermal stability is [Ni(Sal)(OHA)-o-PhDA] (220°) ~ [Ni(NaPh)(OHA)-o-PhDA] (220°) ~ [Ni(Sal)(NaPh)-o-PhDA] (220°) > [Ni(Sal)(OHA)-p-PhDA] (200°) ~ [Ni(NaPh)(OHA)-p-PhDA] (200°) > [Ni(Sal)(NaPh)-p-PhDA] (180°).

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Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Iron(II) Complexes of 3-Carboxy-4-Hydroxy Azobenzene as Indicators in Acid Base Titrations

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THE use of metal complexes as visual indicators in acid base titrations has been investigated in recent years¹⁻⁴. Zinc(II), cadmium(II) and manganese(II) complexes of 1-[2-pyridylazo]-2-phenanthrol (PAP) have been used as indicators in the titration of strong base against strong acid⁵. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to study the use of metal complexes of 3-carboxy-4-hydroxy azobenzene (CHAB) as indicators in acid base titrations.

Experimental

3-Carboxy-4-hydroxy azobenzene: Aniline was diazotised and immediately coupled with salicylic acid in alkaline medium. The solution was then acidified with dilute acetic acid and the yellowish

orange CHAB formed was filtered and crystallised from ethanol/methanol.

Metal complexes: Copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes were prepared by refluxing the solutions of metal chlorides with CHAB in alcohol. A little sodium acetate was added⁶. The Fe(II) complex was prepared by refluxing a solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate with CHAB in alcohol in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The excess of metal or ligand was removed by washing with hot distilled water⁷. The Cu(II) complex is reddish yellow while those of Ni(II) and Fe(II) are yellow and reddish brown, respectively.

Indicator solution: The indicator solution was prepared by dissolving 200 mg of a complex in 100 ml methanol. Freshly prepared 0.2% solutions were used as indicators.

Method of titration:

10 ml 0.1 M hydrochloric acid was pipetted into a conical flask and about 0.5 ml 0.2% indicator solution was added. The acid was then titrated against 0.1 M sodium hydroxide solution. The sharp colour change from colourless to turmeric yellow was the end point.

Results and Discussion

Titration precision:

Eight titrations were performed with each indicator and the ability of the indicators to change colour was tested. The precision obtained from each set is given below:

Indicator	Maximum deviation from the mean	Average deviation from the mean
Cu(II)-CHAB complex	0.05%	0.05%
Ni(II)-CHAB complex	0.05%	0.05%
Fe(II)-CHAB complex	0.05%	0.05%

Effect of the concentration of indicators:

Changing the concentration of the indicator solution from 0.2 to 0.5% in all the cases did not affect the titration results. So, 0.5 ml 0.2% indicator solution is recommended for titration. Less than 0.5 ml of the indicator gives false end points due to indistinguishable colour change.

pH and temperature range for colour change:

It has been found that the pH range for colour change is 6.5 to 8.0 for the said complexes. The titration of strong acid and strong base can be carried out in the 25 to 40° temperature range.

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Polarographic Studies of Acetylacetonate Complexes of Pb(II) and Mn(II)

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IN aqueous solutions acetylacetonate is a weak acid with a pK_a value¹⁻⁴ of 8.95. It readily forms⁵ stable metal chelates. Branica and coworkers⁶⁻¹⁰ undertook polarographic investigations of acetylacetonate complexes of UO₂(II), Cu(II), Co(II) and Ni(II). Aihara and Misumi¹¹ studied polarographic behaviour of Ni(II), Cr(III) and Co(II) acetylacetonate complexes in N,N-dimethyl formamide and found their reduction irreversible. Recently, Singh *et al*^{12,13} have determined polarographically the composition and stability constants of Cd(II) and Zn(II) acetylacetonate complexes. A survey of literature reveals that polarographic behaviour of Pb(II) and Mn(II) in acetylacetonate has not been studied so far. The present study was, therefore, undertaken with a view to determining the composition and the stability of acetylacetonate complexes of Pb(II) and Mn(II).

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade and their stock solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The strength of the solutions of Pb(NO₃)₂ and MnCl₂ was determined by standard methods. Acetylacetonate was a B.D.H., A.R. (England) product. The concentration of each depolarizer in the final solution to be polarographed was maintained at 1.0×10^{-8} M. NaClO₄ was used as a supporting electrolyte in the case of Mn(II) while NaNO₃ was used in the case of Pb(II), as Pb(II) formed a precipitate with sodium perchlorate. Requisite amount (0.001%) of Triton X-100 was added in each case to suppress the maxima. The studies were done at a constant ionic strength $\mu=0.1$ (NaNO₃ or NaClO₄) and constant temperature ($25 \pm 0.1^\circ$) and a constant pH. Purified nitrogen was passed through the solutions to remove the dissolved oxygen. Polarograms of the solutions were taken using a manual polarograph, Toshniwal CLO2, in conjunction with a Toshniwal polyflex galvanometer PL 50. Saturated calomel electrode was used as a reference electrode. The capillary characteristics in the two systems have been mentioned in the respective Tables. The number of electrons 'n' involved in the reduction of acetyl-